

Partially Regularized Ordinal Regression to Measure Impacts of Complementary Unit Performance in American College Football

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Abstract

American football is quite unique in the sense that the same team's offensive and defensive units typically consist of separate player sets that don't share the field simultaneously, which tempts one to evaluate them independently. Yet, some aspects of your team's defensive (offensive) performance tend to complement your offense (defense, respectively), e.g. turnovers forced by your defense could lead to easier scoring chances for your offense. We leverage detailed sequential drive-by-drive data from the 2014-2020 college football seasons in order to identify the features of complementary football that impact scoring the most, subsequently adjusting each team's offensive (defensive) performance to project it onto a league-average complementary unit. In particular, we conduct regularized ordinal regression modeling with an elastic penalty that allows variable selection with an added novelty of partial relaxation for the proportional odds assumption. Moreover, given the importance of contextualized team rankings in college football, we incorporate unpenalized components to guarantee the full adjustment of each team's scoring for the strength of their respective schedules and the home-field factor. For residual diagnostics of our ordinal regression models we apply the surrogate approach, creatively extending its use to non-proportional odds models.

Keywords: elastic net, LASSO, ordinal regression, proportional odds, residual diagnostics, sports analytics

1 Introduction

In the rapidly developing field of sports analytics immense progress has been made in developing metrics for performance evaluation, be it for an individual player or team as a whole. It would range from sophisticated formulas leveraging basic box scores to calculate a player quality rating (e.g. offensive/defensive rating in basketball (Oliver, 2004), or quarterback rating in football (Oliver, 2011)), to increasingly detailed record-keeping for statistics like actions/dribbles per touch or seconds it takes for QB to throw, to incorporating technological advancements in allowing things like spatial data tracking ((Shea, 2014)). According to (Shea, 2014), evaluation of a player or a team is comprised of two main dimensions: production and context. Most of the findings listed so far have to do predominantly with evaluating production: the volume of statistical output a player/team generates, efficiency with which it's generated, etc. Context, on the other hand, has more to do with accounting for the factors surrounding the production, which may include: opponent, teammates, whether the game is at home or away, etc. In this work, we will focus on accounting for context in the sport of American college football, where the importance of fully-contextualized team evaluation is especially elevated for the reasons outlined below.

Football Bowl Subdivision (FBS) of Division-I American college football, as of 2022, consists of 131 participating college football programs, split into 11 conferences. Each team is scheduled to play only 12 opponents during regular season, mostly within their own conference. Given that at the end of the season all FBS teams need to be ranked in deciding who goes on to the playoffs and bowl games, such format leaves gaps in understanding the context of relative quality of opposition each team might have faced during the season. To account for the potential differences in strength of schedule, an "offense-defense" model was introduced in (Harville, 1977) (and later also leveraged by (Govan et al., 2009) in college basketball and professional American football), where team's scoring is assumed to be a function of their offense and opponent's defense, hereby adjusting for strength of the opposition. Moreover, given the importance of home-field advantage (Edwards and Archambault, 1979; Vergin and Sosik, 1999), the model in (Harville, 1977) also accounted for whether a team played most of its games at home or away.

In this work, besides adjusting for the strength of schedule and home field factor, in evaluating each team's offense and defense we wanted to also incorporate the adjustment for the complementary nature of the game. Unlike most other sports, in American football offense and defense are typically played by non-overlapping sets of players that don't take the field at the same time. It could lead one to assuming that performance of a team's offense deserves to be treated independently of that same team's defense. Nonetheless, there are reasons to believe that the two sides complement each other. For example, turnovers forced by your defense could lead to easier scoring chances for your offense while, on the other hand, your offense's ability to control the clock may help your defense rest and recover. That concept has been termed "complementary football", and it hasn't been given much attention in literature on contextualized football team evaluation, which is why it constitutes the focus of this work.

We leverage detailed sequential drive-by-drive data from the 2014-2020 American college football seasons, where "drive" means a continuous possession of the ball by one team,

and a tailored regularized estimation technique of ordinal regression with partial elastic net penalty, in order to conduct variable selection of the most critical features of complementary football in collegiate game. More specifically, we utilize the optimization framework introduced in (Wurm et al., 2021) to relax the proportional odds assumption of ordinal regression models, but we further extend its penalization scheme. Our extension allows a guaranteed inclusion of proportional-odds coefficients for a set of predictors without the necessity to always include their non-proportional counterparts, considerably simplifying the estimation task. Moreover, with the residual diagnostics not as developed for categorical models as they are for classical regression, we leverage a surrogate approach introduced in (Liu and Zhang, 2018) specifically for ordinal regression models. Although not extending on their methodology, we have enhanced their *R* package *sure* (Greenwell et al., 2018) by allowing it to handle regularized ordinal regression fits and also yield residual diagnostics for non-proportional odds models.

Among previous work done on adjusting for complementary nature of American football, (Skripnikov, 2023) attempted an analogous task, but they have dealt with cumulative game totals instead of sequential data, failing to capture the direct impact of one unit’s performance on their complementary side’s outcome in the subsequent drive. (Yurko et al., 2019) developed a framework to estimate the expected points generated by each play based on the game context (down, distance, time left, etc), allowing to split credit between units of a football team, but they didn’t carry out an explicit projection onto a league-average complementary unit, and didn’t conduct variable selection across different statistical categories accumulated on the preceding drive while accounting for strength of the opponent (making this work tailored to college football in particular). Outside of that, related ideas were studied in other sports. (Kempton et al., 2016) modeled expected points for rugby plays based on the starting field position of the current possession and the outcome of the previous possession. (Boshnakov et al., 2017) analyzed the dependence between goals scored and allowed by a team in a soccer match. Unlike American football, those other sports have a much more continuous flow between offensive and defensive play, with the same players being involved in both facets while always sharing the field at the same time. Therefore, attempts to adjust the evaluation of the team’s offense for the quality of their own defense, and vice versa, doesn’t make as much practical sense as it does with American football, where offense and defense are played by separate sets of players.

The remaining structure of the paper is as follows. Section 2 describes the data cleaning and outlines all the modeling considerations, including preliminary model diagnostics for classic ordinal regression fits, main partial regularization criteria with the proportional odds assumption relaxation, and residual diagnostics for the selected reduced modeling fits. Section 3 covers the variable selection stability analysis, describing the nature of complementary football effects on scoring outcome probabilities and expected points per drive, wrapping by a demonstration of college football ranking modifications. Lastly, conclusions and broader discussion of our main takeaways, along with description of avenues for future work, are presented in Section 4.

2 Materials and methods

2.1 Data collection and cleaning

Play-by-play data for 2014-2020 FBS seasons were obtained via *cfbfastR* Gilani et al. (2022) package of *R* Statistical Software (R Core Team, 2020). Although the data set is thorough, extensive data cleaning was conducted to make the format more appropriate for our analysis and resolve various inconsistencies such as lack of continuity in field positions between consecutive plays, discrepancies between play yardage values and the differences in field positions, occasional mismatch between play text and numerical entries, to name a few. First, we have removed the overtime plays, as the overtime format in college football differs considerably from the regular format (Wilson, 2020) in ways that virtually eliminate the complementary dimensions of the game. Next, despite our best efforts to correct data inconsistencies that we were able to verify (via cross-checking the play text, yardages, field positions, etc), plenty of observations remained where we couldn't confirm the veracity of their contents, and hence had to be dropped. Due to the importance of sequential nature of drives in American football, we could not simply drop a single play - or even a single drive - without it impacting that structure, and instead we decided to drop the entire half of the game during which the faulty observation(s) occurred. Given the fact that each half of the game starts with a kickoff, unaffected by a previous drive, it can be treated as a continuous standalone period where the complementary nature of football can be measured. After having dropped the faulty halves, we ended up retaining 65% of the initial total of halves, which still provided us with upwards of 15,000 drives in each season (besides 2020 that got shortened due to COVID, resulting in 9,000 drives), averaging around 55-60 drives on which we were able to evaluate each team's offensive and defensive units.

The play-by-play data were subsequently summarized and grouped by drives, calculating the drive's total yards gained, completed and incomplete passes, positive and negative rushing plays, sacks, fumbles, first downs gained, third downs converted, etc. Moreover, to incorporate what happens during plays like field goal kicks, punts and kickoffs - known in American football as "special teams" - we have treated field goal kicking and kick/punt returning as part of the offense, while the opposing end of it - field goal blocking, kick/punt coverage - as part of the defense. For full glossary of calculated statistics, see supplementary materials. Given that only one of the team's units can be on the field during a single drive (either offense or defense), and that they typically switch on consecutive drives, that drive-by-drive format is more conducive to studying the direct effects the defense's (offense's) performance on the current drive would have on its own complementary offense's (defense's, respectively) output during the next drive.

Lastly, with some of the scheduled games for each FBS team traditionally happening against non-major college teams from lower divisions, we create a single "Non-Major" category to which all such opponents are assigned. It allows to incorporate such games into ranking calculations, while avoiding having to create a separate parameter for every single non-major team to be estimated based on a small sample of games.

Table 1: Scoring outcomes of a single drive and their point value designations.

Outcome	Points
1. Defensive Touchdown	-7 ¹
2. Safety	-2
3. No Score	0
4. Field Goal	3
5. Offensive Touchdown	7 ¹

¹Can also be 6 or 8 points, albeit rarely.

2.2 Categorical ordinal nature of points scored during a drive

In American football, a single drive can result in one of five ordinal scoring outcomes outlined in Table 1. The highest positive value is 7 for the offensive touchdown, which is typically comprised of 6 points for getting into the opponent’s endzone, plus an extra point kick. Sometimes the offense decides to go for a two-point play, which is substantially tougher to execute than the kick but, if converted, would give them two extra points instead of one. Therefore, offensive touchdown can result in 7 (made extra point kick), 8 (made two-point attempt) or 6 points (missed extra kick or failed two-point attempt). Despite that, 7 points is by far the most typical result of a touchdown outcome, hence we decide to simplify the point designations. All of the above applies to the defensive touchdown score as well, with the caveat that it counts as a negative value for the offense.

Despite each scoring outcome having a numerical value assigned to it, classic linear regression is not appropriate here due to the categorical nature of the mechanism by which these values are produced. Instead, we leverage ordinal regression approaches, where the focus is on modeling the probabilities of these categorical ordinal outcomes. It presents a much more appropriate modeling framework which would then subsequently allow us to designate the numerical values to the categorical outcomes in a weighted fashion, still lending itself to an intuitive interpretation and helping generate college football rankings for expected points per drive scored and allowed.

2.3 Baseline ordinal regression model

Below we introduce the notation, main modeling considerations, and the baseline model which we used as a starting point for our analyses.

Let c denote the enumeration of the scoring outcome listed in Table 1, $c = 1, 2, \dots, 5$. For a total of n teams in the league, let Y_{ijk} denote the categorical outcome of points scored by the offense of team i against the defense of team j during the k^{th} drive of the game, $i, j = 1, \dots, n$. We assume Y_{ijk} to have a multinomial distribution with vector $\boldsymbol{\pi}_{ijk} = (\pi_{1,ijk}, \dots, \pi_{5,ijk})^\top$, where $\pi_{c,ijk} = P(Y_{ijk} = c)$, $c = 1, \dots, 5$. To account for the ordinal nature of our response variable, we use a cumulative probability approach of modeling the odds of the response category being greater or equal than c , $c = 2, 3, 4, 5$. Our baseline model to account for strength of schedule, home-field factor, and the performance statistics

that the complementary unit exhibited on the *prior* drive, would look as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}
 Y_{ijk} &\sim_{ind.} Multinomial(\boldsymbol{\pi}_{ijk}), \\
 \log\left(\frac{P(Y_{ijk} \geq c)}{P(Y_{ijk} < c)}\right) &= \mu_c + \alpha_i + \beta_j + \delta h_{ij} + \xi I.cmp_{ijk} + \boldsymbol{\gamma}^\top \mathbf{x}_{ji}^* \times I.cmp_{ijk},
 \end{aligned} \tag{1}$$

where μ_c denotes the cumulative odds of the respective scoring category c simultaneously for both the offense and defense of what we will call a "league-average" opponent. As one team's offense scores points, the opponent's defense allows those points - a symmetry which allows for μ_c to represent league averages for both offense and defense at once, and subsequently help project each team's performance onto that same league-average opponent for the eventual ranking purposes. To represent each team's offensive and defensive strength we use $\boldsymbol{\alpha} = (\alpha_1, \dots, \alpha_n)^\top$ and $\boldsymbol{\beta} = (\beta_1, \dots, \beta_n)^\top$ coefficients, respectively. α_i is the margin of offensive improvement for team i over the league-average opponent, while β_j is the defensive margin of improvement for team j . We have set up the contrasts so that $\sum_{i=1}^n \alpha_i = \sum_{j=1}^n \beta_j = 0$, allowing for interpretation of the intercept term as the league-average opponent. Additionally, h_{ij} denotes homefield indicator for the game between teams i and j , taking on value 1 if team i is designated as the home team, and 0 otherwise. Therefore, coefficient δ will serve to represent the impact of homefield advantage.

Lastly, as the main novelty and contribution of this work to the application domain, vector $\boldsymbol{\gamma} = (\gamma_1, \dots, \gamma_L)^\top$ will contain the effects of all L complementary statistics $\mathbf{x}_{jik}^* = (x_{1,jik}^*, \dots, x_{L,jik}^*) = (x_{1,jik} - \bar{x}_1, \dots, x_{L,jik} - \bar{x}_L)$ that team j 's offense accumulated against team i 's defense (hence the flipped notation of "ji" instead of "ij") on the *previous drive*. Such incorporation of previous drive data allows us to evaluate the sequential complementary impact the same team's offense and defense could have on one another. The statistics centered by subtracting the mean, allowing to interpret the intercept terms μ_c and offensive/defensive margins (α_i/β_j) as projections onto the league-average *complementary unit* performance, besides just the league-average opponent.

The model (1) has an important caveat: roughly 10% of drives are either not preceded by any other drive (e.g. at the start of the game or half), or follow a drive by the same team's offense (after a defensive touchdown score, where the same offense that allowed it has to come back onto the field for the next drive). Despite such cases not contributing to the study of direct impacts of complementary football, we still needed to include these observations for the purpose of incorporating the points scored during these drives into the eventual estimate of the respective team's offensive and defensive worth. To achieve that, we included a $\mathbf{x}_{jik}^* \times I.cmp_{ijk}$ term, where $I.cmp_{ijk}$ is an indicator variable taking on value 1 for drives where the effects of complementary football could be estimated, and 0 otherwise, in the latter case annulling the part of the model responsible for those effects. We also added a marginal term $\xi I.cmp_{ijk}$ for this indicator, which allows us to interpret $\boldsymbol{\gamma}^\top$ coefficients solely as the effects of complementary statistics \mathbf{x}_{jik}^* when $I.cmp_{ijk} = 1$, as opposed to also conflating it with changes in $I.cmp$ value (which, with the inclusion of the marginal term, would now also involve the ξ coefficient).

All-in-all, model (1) achieves three goals at once. It allows to project each team's performance onto the same league-average opponent, home/away scheduling balance, and

league-average complementary unit. All of the above helps with a more thorough and contextualized evaluation of each team’s performance up to that point in the season.

2.4 Preliminary model diagnostics

To gauge how appropriate our ordinal modeling approach was, we carried out a check for multi-collinearity and preliminary residual diagnostics for the baseline model (1) and several of its extensions. The highest variance inflation factor values would not exceed the value of 10 by much, indicating only a slight evidence of collinearity not projected to impact the modeling performance as much. For the residual analysis, we referred to a surrogate approach introduced in (Liu and Zhang, 2018) specifically for ordinal regression models. It involves generating surrogate residuals based on a continuous latent variable interpretation of cumulative link ordinal regression models, which results in more intuitive diagnostics of residual patterns. It is implemented in package *sure* (Greenwell et al., 2018) which helps produce the familiar residuals-vs-fitted and quantile-quantile (QQ) plots with the identical pattern expectations to that of the residuals for classic linear regression with a continuous response. After having run it for our baseline model (1) across all seven college football seasons, the diagnostics indicated a good fit. For details on one of the seasons, see supplementary materials.

Next, with our drive-by-drive data format having a clear grouping of observations by the game, it is natural to check whether there might be within-game error correlation that would violate the independence assumption of our baseline model (1). We used the function *clmm* of the *ordinal* package (Christensen, 2022) to run a mixed-effects cumulative link model that would incorporate a random intercept term for the *game_id* variable. Having run that mixed model and subsequently conducted a likelihood ratio test comparing it to the baseline fixed-effects model, it showed no statistical evidence of within-group dependence for any of the seven college seasons under consideration.

Therefore, the baseline model (1) has been shown as a reasonable starting point in terms of the modeling fit and satisfaction of the most crucial assumptions. One assumption imposed by model (1) that we are yet to check is that of proportional odds. It states that the impact of a variable on the cumulative odds of category c_1 is proportional to its impact on the cumulative odds of category c_2 , $c_1 \neq c_2$, implying that all the non-intercept coefficients - $\alpha, \beta, \delta, \xi, \gamma$ - are not dependent on the category c under consideration. Although simplifying the estimation process considerably, this assumption can be quite restrictive in reality. Section 2.5 below describes the regularized estimation approach that we leveraged in order to strike a balance between variable selection, efficient estimation and relaxing the proportional odds assumption.

2.5 Variable selection methodology outline

As mentioned in Section 2.4, our baseline model (1) imposes a rather restrictive assumption of proportional odds. If one were to fully relax that restriction, it would replace the single coefficient vectors $\alpha^{n \times 1}, \beta^{n \times 1}, \gamma^{L \times 1}$ with four sets of each, one per cumulative probability category: $\alpha_c^{n \times 1}, \beta_c^{n \times 1}, \gamma_c^{L \times 1}$, $c = 2, \dots, 5$. It would increase the number of parameters to

be estimated from 275 to 1100, making the task much more complex. As an alternative, we implemented a regularization approach that introduces a partial elastic net penalty structure allowing one to relax the proportional odds assumption while still keeping the estimation task feasible.

First, given that the offensive and defensive margin coefficients ($\boldsymbol{\alpha}$ and $\boldsymbol{\beta}$) warrant a high number of parameters as it is (260), allowing these coefficients to differ by response category would contribute to the increased complexity of the estimation task the most. Furthermore, with team ranking considerations in mind, our plan is to guarantee inclusion of each team’s defensive and offensive coefficients in the final model by leaving them unpenalized. It helps put more emphasis on the games that the teams actually did play, as opposed to optimizing the out-of-sample predictive ability typically granted by shrinkage, while also virtually guaranteeing that the resulting estimates won’t have any rank ties. Therefore, in regards to the offensive/defensive margin coefficients, we can’t expect a significant model simplification due to the feature selection aspect of the elastic net penalty. Due to all of the above, the offensive and defensive margin coefficients will be left unpenalized and consistent across all the response categories.

Second, for the L complementary football features, which require a considerably smaller number of parameters (15 in the baseline model), we can reasonably relax the proportional odds requirement without sacrificing as much in estimation feasibility. For that, we will pursue the semi-parallel optimization approach introduced in (Wurm et al., 2021) and implemented in their *ordinalNet* package:

$$\begin{aligned} \min_{\substack{\boldsymbol{\mu}, \boldsymbol{\delta}, \boldsymbol{\alpha}, \boldsymbol{\beta} \\ \boldsymbol{\gamma}, \{\boldsymbol{\gamma}_c\}_2^5}} & -\frac{1}{N^*} \ell(\boldsymbol{\mu}, \boldsymbol{\alpha}, \boldsymbol{\beta}, \boldsymbol{\delta}, \boldsymbol{\xi}, \boldsymbol{\gamma}, \boldsymbol{\gamma}_2, \dots, \boldsymbol{\gamma}_5; \mathbf{y}) + \lambda((\alpha \|\boldsymbol{\gamma}\|_1 + \frac{1}{2}(1 - \alpha) \|\boldsymbol{\gamma}\|_2^2) + \\ & + (\sum_{c=2}^5 (\alpha \|\boldsymbol{\gamma}_c\|_1 + \frac{1}{2}(1 - \alpha) \|\boldsymbol{\gamma}_c\|_2^2))) \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

where $\ell()$ is the multinomial log-likelihood function which, for all the complementary football features $\mathbf{x} = (x_1, \dots, x_L)^\top$, includes both the proportional odds model coefficients $\boldsymbol{\gamma}$ and the non-proportional ones $\boldsymbol{\gamma}_c$ for cumulative odds of response category $c, c = 2, \dots, 5$. It is derived from a modified version of our baseline model 1 where the right-hand side of the equation linking the parameters to predictors would represent the effect of complementary football features as $\boldsymbol{\gamma}^\top \mathbf{x}_{ji} + \boldsymbol{\gamma}_c^\top \mathbf{x}_{ji}$ instead of just $\boldsymbol{\gamma}^\top \mathbf{x}_{ji}$. Such formulation allows to select, for each feature, either a proportional odds model (by setting all the non-proportional coefficients to zero) or incorporate the non-proportional coefficients to relax the restrictive assumption. On the downside, such parameterization leads to a model that is not identifiable, but that is precisely where the elastic penalty (Zou and Hastie, 2005) in the second row of the optimization criteria (2) comes in. It results from a weighted combination of LASSO and ridge penalties, where $\alpha \in [0, 1]$ dictates the weight distribution. $\alpha = 1$ would correspond to pure LASSO penalty, $\alpha = 0$ represents ridge, and $\alpha \in (0, 1)$ is a mixture of the two. (Wurm et al., 2021) have shown that, despite the overparameterized formulation, optimization task (2) is guaranteed to have a unique optimum for all the cases besides $\alpha = 1$ (pure LASSO). Given that the main focus of this work is feature selection, which is

achieved specifically by the LASSO penalty, we used a high α value of 0.99 so as to avoid the non-unique optimum while keeping the emphasis on variable selection.

Although the main optimization algorithm for the task (2) is implemented in the *ordinalNet* package, it wouldn't allow one to include the non-proportional coefficients solely for a subset of predictors, which prompted us to extend their source code to accommodate this task. To select the tuning parameter value λ , we leveraged 10-fold cross-validation (CV). In particular, we picked the λ value that achieved test error within one standard deviation of the minimal test error while providing a sparser model ("sparse CV"). Such an approach emphasizes selection of simple models with the most critical variables, virtually guaranteeing that the selected complementary football features would have gotten picked by any other ubiquitous criteria as well. Lastly, to mitigate the randomness effect of the 10-fold CV procedure, we ran three replicates for each model. For the final evaluation of selection stability, we calculated the selection proportions across all replicates and seasons, accounting for the coefficient signs as well.

2.6 Post-hoc analysis of selected features

Having identified the most consistent features of complementary football, we refitted the ordinal regression models to only include those features. This step allows us to study the nature of the selected complementary football effects across the years, guaranteeing consistency in ranking adjustment patterns. Given that we ended up consistently selecting some non-proportional odds coefficients for cumulative odds of just one (rather than all categories) category, and that there were no packages implementing such an exact specification, we further enhanced the *ordinalNet* package (Wurm et al., 2021) to allow for their algorithm to be applicable in such cases.

To conduct a post-hoc analysis of the selected model's quality of fit, much like during the preliminary analysis, we referred to the surrogate residuals approach (Liu and Zhang, 2018) carried out in the *sure* package (Greenwell et al., 2018), but this time with a methodological modification. It's important to note that the surrogate approach mechanism is capable of yielding a reasonable single set of surrogate residuals for the entire ordinal regression fit solely in the case of a proportional odds fit. Therefore, to make it more appropriate for our scenario of a non-proportional odds model, we calculated surrogate residuals for our model's fit to each cumulative odds separately. That meant treating each fitted equation from model (1) as a separate binary logistic regression, and subsequently producing a separate set of residuals and diagnostic plots for each such equation, which the surrogate approach allowed. We called it a "binarized diagnostics" approach, and proceeded to enhance the source code of the *sure* package in order to incorporate that functionality.

To study the nature of the effect the selected complementary football features had on scoring, we produced prediction plots that would demonstrate the impact on probabilities of scoring outcome categories. Additionally, we converted the vector of predicted probabilities into expected points scored via weighting them by point value designations from Table 1, which helped illustrate the complementary football features' impact on the expected points per possession. Lastly, to calculate the college rankings in points per possession scored (offense) and allowed (defense), for each team we would: first, calculate the cumulative

odds estimates of their offensive and defensive performance in scoring category c against the league-average opponent, with the league-average complementary unit, and league-average proportion of scheduled home games; second, convert those into probabilities; third, calculate the weighted average of expected points as described before.

3 Results

In this section we start off by presenting the results of running the optimization task (2) and evaluating selection stability of complementary football features. After having identified the most consistently selected features, we illustrate the nature of their impact on scoring in college football. We wrap up by demonstrating the ranking adjustments that result from projecting each team’s offensive/defensive performance onto the league-average complementary unit, on top of the strength-of-schedule and home-field adjustments.

3.1 Selection stability analysis

On Figure 1a we present selection stability results of optimization task (2) for each football statistic (rows), specifically its proportional odds coefficient of affecting all scoring categories (first column) and non-proportional odds coefficients of impacting one of the cumulative odds (columns 2 through 5), including the signs of respective coefficients. We will initially focus on the first column, as it represents an effect on all categories. The non-scoring takeaway indicator gets selected in 90% of the cases and always shows a positive effect on scoring, meaning that a non-scoring takeaway generated by the defense on the previous drive typically leads to more points scored by the offense on the current drive. Figure 2 demonstrates the intuition of this result due to the field position implications for the offense: whenever the complementary defense gets a takeaway and your offense takes the field, it has considerably fewer yards to go until the opponent’s endzone (median of 51 as opposed to 78), making for an easier scoring opportunity, while also decreasing the chances of the opposing defense to score a defensive touchdown or a safety.

In the meantime, yards gained by the opposing offense (same as allowed by your own defense) got selected in 60% of the cases, which is still considerably higher than for the next closest feature, and respectable if one recalls that we are using an especially harsh penalty tuning parameter selection criteria. It has always shown a negative impact on your offense’s scoring, which can be attributed to two aspects. First, high yardages allowed by your defense tend to yield worse starting field position for your own offense on the subsequent drive. To be more specific, such cases typically imply either a score by the opponent, which results in a kickoff that has your offense start from deep in their own territory, or a punt that pins your offense really deep without a good opportunity to return it. Secondly, the more yards your defense gives up on a drive, the longer the opposing defense typically gets to rest and recover on the sidelines, meaning they would be fresher when facing your own offense during the subsequent drive. In American football, the recovery time is especially important for defenses due to the fact that the offense is in control of the ball and gets to dictate the pace of the game, while the defense has to constantly react.

	All Categ.	\geq Safety	\geq No Score	\geq FG	\geq Off. TD
off.ST.yards.gained	-0.6	0.0	0.0	-0.9	0.0
ST.return.yards.net	0.0	0.0	0.0	-0.1	0.0
pts.scored	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
first.downs.gained	-0.2	0.0	0.0	-0.3	0.0
third.downs.converted	0.0	0.0	0.0	-0.2	0.0
takeaway.nonscor	0.9	0.0	0.0	0.9	0.0
turnover.nonscor	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
punt.safety	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
n.completions	-0.1	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
n.incompletions	-0.0	0.0	0.0	-0.0	0.0
n.positive.runs	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
n.stuffed.runs	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
n.negative.plays	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
n.sacks	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
n.fumbles	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.4	0.0

(a) Selection stability

(b) Starting field position

Figure 1: (a): Proportion of seasons and replicates when a proportional (first column) or non-proportional (columns 2-5, by response category) odds coefficient for each complementary football statistic (rows) was chosen in how it impacts scoring on subsequent drive, including the coefficient sign. (b): Box plots of starting field positions (yards to goal) for the offense depending on whether there was a non-scoring takeaway by the defense on the previous drive. In case of returned punts and kickoffs, the starting field position is counted from the moment the returner caught the ball.

Among other consistently selected coefficients, Figure 1a shows that both the non-scoring takeaways and yards gained also got selected 90% of the time as having a non-proportional effect on the odds of scoring at least a field goal on the next drive (see the " $\geq FG$ " column). It indicates that, while having an effect on all cumulative scoring odds, these two statistics exhibit an even stronger impact when distinguishing drives that ended in an offensive score (field goal or touchdown) as opposed to not. The effect of non-scoring takeaways becomes more positive, while the yards gained by the opposing offense - more negative. This result can be explained by the following intuition: both of the complementary statistics have strong implications for the starting field position on the next drive. For example, see Figure 1b for the case of non-scoring takeaways. Given that most kickers can reliably make a field goal starting from 30 yards to go, it implies a median of only 21 yards for your offense to gain before it gets within that range. To reach the opponent's endzone for a touchdown, on the other hand, would require them to gain another 30 yards. What makes the latter task even harder is the fact that, as the offense nears the opposing endzone, it has to operate in a more confined space: the endzone itself is only 10 yards deep, and the offensive players have to stay inside the lines, hence they don't have as many options for deep passing plays and maneuvering, making them easier to defend against. For example, if an offense needs to gain 10 yards from 10 yards to go as

Figure 2: Effects of yards gained (left) and non-scoring takeaway indicator (right) on each scoring outcome probability for the offense during the subsequent drive for the league-average team during the 2016 season.

opposed to from 40 yards to go, the defense has to cover only 20 yards of depth contrary to 50. Given all of the above, it's not surprising to see a good starting position having an especially strong effect on offenses scoring at least a field goal, but not necessarily on them scoring a touchdown, because the latter strongly depends on the offense's ability to operate in the confined space of what's typically referred to as the "red zone" (20 yards to go).

Figure 2 depicts the effects of selected features on the probabilities of each scoring outcome during 2016 season for the league-average team, which results from averaging the performances of all the teams that year. On the left, there is an evident decrease in probability of scoring at least a field goal (a sum of purple and blue areas) as the yards allowed by your defense on the previous drive increase, while the decline in touchdown probability (purple area) is noticeably slower, which can be attributed in part to the aforementioned discussion of the non-proportional odds coefficient that implies stronger impact on the odds of scoring at least a field goal, as opposed to a touchdown. On the right, there's a clear increase in probability of at least a field goal score after a takeaway, and it's stronger than the increase to the probability of a touchdown for analogous reasons.

To confirm that our reduced non-proportional odds model constituted a proper fit to the data, we leveraged the binarized diagnostics approach inspired by the same surrogate residuals already for the preliminary analysis (Liu and Zhang, 2018) and described in Section 2.6. As can be seen on QQ plots of Figure 3 below (see supplementary materials to also check the residuals-vs-fitted plots), the patterns are indicative of a proper fit for the 2016 season, but the same holds for all the years under consideration. In particular, one can

Figure 3: Binarized surrogate residuals quantile-quantile (QQ) plots for the non-proportional cumulative odds model fit on 2016 season data accounting for the most consistent complementary football features.

see how the sample quantiles align with the theoretical ones for cumulative odds equations across all ordinal response categories. That includes the field goal (FG) category which, as discussed earlier, had non-proportional odds.

Our reduced models allow us to create predictions that help illustrate the nature of the effect the selected complementary features have on the expected points per drive. Figure 4 contains predictions of extra points per drive that each team’s offense is expected to gain after a non-scoring takeaway by their complementary defense, plotted against the baseline of points per drive expected without such a takeaway. For each season it exhibits a parabolic relationship where the gain in expected points from a non-scoring takeaway increases up to 1, but once the offenses start averaging more than 3 points per drive as their baseline, the extra points start going down in big part because of the upper-bound limit of 7 points per drive.

3.2 Ranking shifts in points per drive

Using the 2016 season an example, Table 2 shows the ranking modifications of offenses’ points scored per drive courtesy of adjusting for the complementary football features that got selected in Section 3.1, on top of already accounting for strength of schedule and

Figure 4: Relationship between the offense’s points per drive scored without a defensive takeaway on the previous possession (the ”baseline”) and the extra points expected after such takeaway, projected onto league-average opponent and complementary unit. Each smoothed curve represents a season, each point represents a team.

homefield factor. When reading the results discussion below, one should think of the adjustment for complementary unit performance as a projection of team’s offensive output onto the league-average complementary defense, in addition to projecting them onto the league-average opponent and homefield factor.

First, one can notice the switch between 1st and 2nd place, with Oklahoma’s offense gaining 0.07 points per drive and Michigan’s offense dropping 0.13 points. The reasoning for this switch is evident in their respective teams’ defensive statistics where, while similar with respect to non-scoring takeaways, Michigan’s defense is much better in yards allowed. They rank 7th in the nation compared to Oklahoma’s 103rd, with the latter allowing an average of 13 more yards per drive. Michigan’s offense is the beneficiary of a much better complementary defensive unit than Oklahoma, which prompts our adjustment to penalize Michigan and reward Oklahoma when projecting them onto the league-average complementary defense.

The biggest increases in value from the Top-10 offenses were experienced by Louisiana Tech and Pittsburgh, adding 0.10 and 0.08 points per drive, respectively. That is a direct result of their complementary units ranked really low in both relevant statistical categories (between 97th and 118th, out of 131 teams). With that being said, Oklahoma’s defense appears to be considerably better than both of these units, and yet their offense still gets a

Table 2: Partial 2016 season rankings in points scored per drive by team’s offense, adjusted for strength of schedule, homefield factor, defense’s non-scoring takeaways and yards allowed. Shifts are relative to adjusting only for strength of schedule and homefield factor.

Team	Points Scored (Per Drive)		Defense Statistics (Per Drive)	
	Val (Shift)	Rk (Shift)	Takeaways	Yards Allowed
			Rk (Val)	Rk (Val)
Oklahoma	3.63 (↑ 0.07)	1 (↑ 1)	58 (0.114)	103 (41.5)
Michigan	3.46 (↓ 0.13)	2 (↓ 1)	60 (0.112)	7 (28.3)
Louisiana Tech	3.25 (↑ 0.10)	3 (↑ 1)	97 (0.090)	118 (43.4)
Western Michigan	3.24 (↑ 0.01)	4 (↓ 1)	15 (0.146)	89 (39.2)
Navy	3.20 (↑ 0.06)	5 (=0)	74 (0.104)	127 (45.7)
Pittsburgh	3.18 (↑ 0.08)	6 (↑ 1)	113 (0.069)	108 (42.1)
USC	3.03 (↓ 0.07)	7 (↓ 1)	31 (0.131)	36 (34.1)
Clemson	3.03 (↓ 0.04)	8 (=0)	67 (0.108)	29 (33.0)
Auburn	3.00 (↓ 0.03)	9 (=0)	66 (0.109)	16 (31.0)
Washington State	2.98 (↓ 0.03)	10 (=0)	59 (0.113)	81 (38.5)
....
Washington	2.80 (↓ 0.18)	15 (↓ 3)	3 (0.176)	27 (32.9)
....
Akron	2.00 (↑ 0.14)	59 (↑ 14)	127 (0.045)	128 (46.4)
....

comparable increase in points per drive. Such scenarios could be attributed to two reasons. First, the adjustments depend on the timing of when the offense scored most of their points. For example, if an offense averaged many points on drives not preceded by a non-scoring takeaway or low yardage allowed by the defense, while not scoring as many points on all other drives, they won’t get impacted by the adjustment as much. Secondly, it can be a byproduct of the effect depicted on Figure 4, where the benefits of a non-scoring takeaway start decreasing when offense hits a certain baseline.

To demonstrate the extreme cases, at the bottom of Table 2 we show the offenses that exhibited the largest positive and negative shifts, respectively, in the expected points scored per drive. Washington’s offense benefited from an extremely opportunistic defense (0.176 non-scoring takeaways per drive, 3rd in the nation) that also managed to hold the opponent to low yardages (32.9 yards per drive, ranked 27th), hence got dropped by 0.18 points per drive via our adjustment. Akron offense, on the other hand, received no favors from their complementary defensive unit that ranked in the Bottom-5 of the nation in both non-scoring takeaways and yards allowed, gaining 0.14 extra points per drive due to our modification. Although value shifts of 0.15-0.20 might not seem like much, when one realizes that a typical game has 12 drives per team, it amounts to 2-2.4 points per game, hence 24-30 points throughout a 12-game regular season.

To also check the defensive ranking shifts for the 2016 college football season, which occur simultaneously with the offensive shifts in 2 due to both being estimated within the same optimization criteria (2), see one of the tables in supplementary materials. It

illustrates the defenses complemented by worse offenses in terms their tendency to give the ball away and inability to gain yards, e.g. Florida and Kansas, getting a positive adjustment via our approach that projects them onto the league-average complementary offense (where the latter isn't expected to put them in as many precarious positions). On the other hand, for teams with an offense that takes care of the ball and is capable of gaining yards, such as Ohio State, Michigan, Auburn and Western Michigan, the defense is being docked points in recognition of being a beneficiary of a good complementary offensive unit.

4 Discussion and future work

We have implemented a partially regularized ordinal regression approach to infer the most consistent features of complementary football that affect scoring in American college football, while making sure to account for strength of schedule and home-field factor. It involved us modifying the optimization criteria and coding algorithm made available in (Wurm et al., 2021) to allow for partial introduction of non-proportional odds, which helped make the parameter estimation task more feasible. Additionally, we enhanced the functionality of the *sure* package (Greenwell et al., 2018) to allow application of surrogate approach (Liu and Zhang, 2018) to non-proportional odds models via performing binarized fit diagnostics. Lastly, we have converted probability predictions into expected points via leveraging them as weights for the point values designated to each outcome, allowing us to make direct interpretations of complementary football impacts on the points scored/allowed per drive.

From the results relevant to the application domain, football statistics that were proven to be the most important in impacting the complementary unit were the non-scoring take-aways and yards gained per drive, exhibiting positive and negative effects, respectively. These results are intuitive due to having direct implications for starting field position on the subsequent drive, while higher yards gained on a drive by one's offense are also indicative of a longer time that their complementary defensive unit gets to rest and recover. Moreover, we seamlessly leveraged the findings to create a more contextualized version of offensive and defensive team rankings that not only projects their performance onto a league-average opponent and homefield factor, but also onto a league-average complementary unit.

This work is similar to (Skripnikov, 2023), but it presents a much more detailed and well-thought-out modeling design with the sequential drive-by-drive nature of the game taken into account, as opposed to simply working with game totals which makes one more vulnerable to such issues as reverse causality - a special case of endogeneity (Kmenta, 1986). Nonetheless, it is worth to note that (Skripnikov, 2023) also identified non-scoring takeaways as a critical factor of complementary football that impacts scoring in college football, pointing to replicability of this particular finding. To borrow from a different sport, (Kempton et al., 2016) studied the expected points for rugby plays based on the starting field position of the current drive (which they call "possession") and the outcome of the previous drive. Although rugby, unlike American football, has the same players involved in team's offense and defense, it is similar in its sequential nature of drives and how the starting position can play a role in the scoring outcome. (Kempton et al., 2016)

found, unsurprisingly, that drives starting closer to the opposing goal-line had the highest expected points scored, which strongly aligns with our results. More curiously, they have also identified that the drives directly following an opponent’s error were more likely to lead to a score. Given that in American football a defensive takeaway can be considered as an error by the offense, that finding draws a yet another parallel with our results. Nonetheless, due to the offensive and defensive duties being carried out in rugby by the same players, it is not as intuitive to try and adjust the offensive/defensive performance for that of their ”complementary unit”, reiterating how uniquely appropriate American football is for that particular application. Moreover, our work is more thorough in accounting for aspects like strength of schedule and homefield advantage.

Lastly, we have found an especially strong effect of the identified complementary statistics on the odds of a team scoring at least a field goal, but not necessarily on the odds of them scoring a touchdown. As mentioned in Section 3.1, although a non-scoring takeaway or less yards allowed on a previous drive indeed tend to get your offense closer to the opponent’s endzone, it also leaves less space for the offense to operate in. (McGovern, 2013) analyzed the data on the percentage of times offenses managed to score a touchdown when being within 5-15 yards of the opponent’s endzone and, while closer is generally better, it is far from a guarantee, with percentages ranging from 70% down to 55%. Scoring at least a field goal, on the other hand, is much closer to a virtual guarantee, due to the already mentioned fact that most kickers can reliably make those starting from 30 yards to go, and it is much easier for the offense to get within that range from a good starting field position (if not already there upon taking the field) than reach the endzone.

For future work, we are considering an extension that would explicitly incorporate point values in the optimization procedure, rather than solely relying on the order of scoring categories. As of now, we only introduce the point values in a post-hoc fashion via weighting them by the predicted probabilities when calculating the expected points per drive, but we never leverage those in the parameter estimation itself. With classical regression not being appropriate in our case due to the categorical nature of the way in which our response values are generated, we expect to develop an approach that is able to benefit from knowing the exact point value designations of each scoring outcome, while still accounting for said categorical underlying data-generation mechanism. Moreover, despite their relative rarity, we would like to accommodate into our categorical modeling structure the cases when a touchdown score results in a value other than 7, potentially introducing an extra layer of conditional response probabilities.

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Statements and declarations

Declaration of interest

We confirm that there are no known conflicts of interest associated with this publication and there has been no financial support that could have influenced its outcome.

Data and code availability

Data and source code for this work have been made publicly available on Github via this link: https://github.com/UsDAndreS/PartRegzOrdRegres_CompFB_Paper.

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